

26 March 2002

**Arctic
Research
Consortium
of the
United States**

Member Institutions:

University of Alaska
Anchorage
University of Alaska
Fairbanks
Alaska North Slope Borough
Dept. of Wildlife Management
Arizona State University
Bates College
Brown University
Center for Northern Studies
University of Colorado
Cold Regions Research and
Engineering Laboratory
Dartmouth College
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Simon Stephenson
Arctic Research Support and Logistics Program Manager
Office of Polar Programs, Room 755
National Science Foundation
4201 Wilson Blvd.
Arlington, VA 22230

Dear Mr. Stephenson:

Enclosed is one copy of the 1st Annual Report of the Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. (ARCUS) as required in Section F-1 of Cooperative Agreement OPP-0101279, between the National Science Foundation and ARCUS. The written report is for the period 1 April 2001 through 31 March 2002. Activities carried out in the pre-award period of January through March 2001 are also described in this report and pre-award costs are included in the financial report.

Included in the annual report, as specified in the Cooperative Agreement, are:

- An executive summary outlining the major activities and accomplishments during the period of this cooperative agreement;
- a narrative summary of accomplishments, future plans, and discussion of major change in direction or pace, by individual task;
- a one-page summary showing costs by five major tasks; arctic community science planning, NSF Arctic Sciences Section coordination, arctic science education, information and outreach, and core support (Attachment A).
- an eight-page, multi-column table, by individual activity, showing the currently approved five-year budget, the approved budget for year one, actual expenditures through March 2002, the remaining funds or shortfall expected, and the proposed budget for April 2002-March 2003 (Attachment B);
- a one-page, multi-column table summarizing the entire cooperative agreement by Form 1030 categories and showing the currently approved budget, actual expenditures through March 2002, the remaining funds or shortfall expected, and the proposed budget for April 2002-March 2003 (Attachment C); and
- the proposed budget for April 2002-March 2003 on NSF Form 1030 (Attachment D).

The ARCUS board of directors and staff are pleased at the achievements of the past year and the work accomplished on behalf of the arctic research community and NSF. We look forward to continuing to work with NSF and the arctic research community on these important initiatives. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me.

Sincerely,

Wendy K. Warnick
Executive Director

Enclosures

cc: ARCUS Board of Directors

THE ARCTIC RESEARCH CONSORTIUM OF THE UNITED STATES

Annual Report Cooperative Agreement OPP-0101279 April 2001 through March 2002

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. (ARCUS) has undertaken a variety of activities to enhance NSF arctic research programs, through Cooperative Agreement OPP-0101279. ARCUS has worked with the scientific community to identify new research objectives, logistical requirements, and educational activities that benefit planning and implementation of NSF-supported science initiatives in the Arctic. Specific activities have been organized under four major tasks:

1. Arctic science planning—coordinating science planning for the arctic research community at several levels, including continuing examination of logistical requirements with the goal of improved access for all researchers in the Arctic;
2. Organizational support for research programs included in the Office of Polar Programs Arctic Sciences Section—the Arctic System Science Program, the Arctic Social Sciences Program, and the Arctic Natural Sciences Program;
3. Development and coordination of arctic science educational activities; and
4. Information and outreach activities disseminating timely information about arctic research to scientists, policy and decision-makers, and to the public.

An additional 5th “task” is the provision of core support for ARCUS’ NSF-funded activities—dedicated funding of the infrastructure necessary to support this work regardless of the specific nature of activities from year-to-year.

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

Accomplishments under this major task include activities to address arctic research support and logistics needs, including:

- Updating the arctic logistics recommendations to provide long-term advice on arctic logistics and science support issues for the NSF Office of Polar Programs;
- Continuing develop and maintenance of ALIAS, an arctic research support and logistics web site that serves as an information resource and access point for the research community; and
- Convening a community workshop to prepare recommendations for NSF on potential uses and necessary infrastructure to use Geographic Information Systems (GIS for the benefit of arctic research.
- Reprinting and distributing the brochure for *SEARCH: The Study of Environmental Arctic Change*, for the SEARCH Interagency Working Group and the Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee.

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

Accomplishments under this major task include several activities for the ARCSS Program and the Arctic Social Sciences Program, as well as the development of informational posters on aspects of arctic research for the Arctic Section as a whole.

2.2 ARCTIC SYSTEM SCIENCE (ARCSS) PROGRAM COORDINATION

Activities under this sub-task include:

- Providing organizational support to the work of the ARCSS Committee (AC) and the AC chair.
- Coordinating the community planning process and convening the second ARCSS Program All-Hands workshop in February 2002.

- Establishing and coordinating a Human Dimensions of the Arctic System (HARC) Science Management Office
- Editing and publishing *CHAMP: The Hydrologic Cycle and its Role in Arctic and Global Environmental Change: A Rationale and Strategy for Synthesis Study*.

2.3 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION

Accomplishments under this sub-task included preliminary planning for an arctic social sciences community-wide conference that will be convened in early 2002, publication and ongoing distribution of a book on Greenland security policy, and initial work on a volume compiling research on indigenous observations of Arctic environmental change.

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

Activities under this major task include:

- Coordinating and participating in a community-based collaborative science education project *Eider Journey*, which provides research experiences for arctic students and teachers.
- Collaborating with Arctic Native organizations and arctic researchers to develop indigenous curriculum materials and to return research results to northern communities, and
- Managing an Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series to increase communication and collaboration among the dispersed arctic research community.
- Publishing a report with recommendations from the Arctic Science Education Working Group for the development of research-focused science education programs for the Arctic.

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

Accomplishments related to information distribution and outreach include:

- Publishing and distributing two issues of *Witness the Arctic*, with one additional issue to be published in May 2002.
- Developing and maintaining web-based resources for arctic research.
- Managing the Arctic Info listserver.
- Maintaining and expanding *The Directory of Arctic Researchers*.
- Convening the two-day *Arctic Forum*, a seminar highlighting important arctic research findings, in Arlington, VA in May 2001, as well as publishing the abstract volume from the seminar; and
- Developing an informational publication on the Arctic for a general audience.
- Preparing an Endangered Species Consultation Bulletin to inform researchers and NSF program managers about the federal requirement and the process for consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) regarding potential impacts of research on listed species.

5. CORE SUPPORT

Accomplishments described in Core Support are direct project activities that benefit and support multiple NSF activities that cannot be identified with one specific project.

THE ARCTIC RESEARCH CONSORTIUM OF THE UNITED STATES

1st Annual Report

April 2001–March 2002

OPP-0101279

The narrative describes activity for the period April 2001 through March 2002, the first year of Cooperative Agreement OPP-0101279. Accomplishments and work in progress are described through March 2002. Activities carried out in the pre-award period of January through March 2001 are also described in this report.

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

1.1 Arctic Research Support and Logistics

Accomplishments

- The Research Support and Logistics Working Group (RSLWG) co-chairs Schlosser and Tucker and ARCUS staff met in March 2001 to compile information and early draft material from working group members to prepare a report outline and initial contents.
- RSLWG members met by teleconference in May 2001 and agreed on the categories of information, key issues, and the research themes to be addressed in the updated report. The themes identified for inclusion in the report are:
 - Variability in the physical environment of the Arctic,
 - Biogeochemical cycling and contaminants,
 - Effects of change on biological resources,
 - Dynamics of human systems in the Arctic, and
 - Upper atmosphere and space weather studies.
- Two additional themes emerged from the survey and community discussions that the working group felt were important and should be addressed in the report:
 - Solid earth issues, and
 - Life in extreme environments.
- The RSLWG agreed that the general categories of research support needs identified by the community that will be addressed in the report update include:
 - Safety,
 - Long-term observation systems,
 - Access to modeling capacity and results to develop a predictive capability,
 - Synthesizing local and research based knowledge,
 - Technology investments,
 - Interagency cooperation, and
 - International collaboration and access to critical locations.
- Working group members identified writing assignments and led groups of selected researchers in preparing draft materials for each section of the updated report.
- Co-chairs Schlosser and Tucker presented information at the May 2001 ARCUS annual meeting on the outline and proposed contents of the update to *Logistics Recommendations for an Improved U.S. Arctic Research Capability* and the timeline for development and publication in 2002.
- Working group members reviewed the first draft of the updated report in November and December 2001.
- The working group met in December 2001 in San Francisco at a meeting of opportunity in conjunction with the American Geophysical Union Fall Meeting to discuss and revise the first draft of the report.
- A revised draft was sent to the working group for review and additional contributions in January 2002.
- RSLWG co-chair Terry Tucker met with ARCUS staff March 2002 to discuss progress and identify outstanding contributions.

Projected Activities

- Compile and integrate working group and invited contributions. Circulate a revised draft report to the working group for review in May 2002.
- Revise the draft report based on working group comments and circulate for open community review in June 2002.
- Revise draft report in July 2002, based on comments received during community review.
- Publish final report in August 2002.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

In August 2001, working group co-chairs Schlosser and Tucker revised the timeline for completion of the report from April 2002 to June 2002. In March 2002, Tucker estimated completion would take until August 2002. The goals and scope of the activities are unchanged.

1.2 Logistics Internet Resources; Arctic Logistics Information and Support (ALIAS)

Accomplishments

- Implemented the final ALIAS web site design and structure <<http://www.arcus.org/alias>>.
- Developed basic field site and platform sections of ALIAS. ALIAS now contains information about many field sites in the Arctic, including contact information, logistics support providers, permitting requirements, access issues, and links to other resources.
- Rebuilt the web site display for faster loading times and cross platform function.
- Completed interactive graphics displays for all arctic regions.
- Publicly announced the availability of the site online.
- Evaluated software options for database support of content and contracted with a database developer.
- Designed a survey format and content for resource manager input.
- Field-tested and revised the input survey.
- Designed the database structure in discussions with the contracted developer.
- Tested, revised and integrated the major components: Input, Database, and Display, which will comprise the final dynamic web site. This activity is ongoing.
- Prepared a “packaged” presentation about ALIAS contents and function for use by the NSF Arctic Section head, Tom Pyle, at meetings during the Arctic Science Summit Week in Groningen, The Netherlands, 21-27 April 2002.
- As it is developed, ALIAS will help researchers to assess the feasibility of working in a specific area, plan the conduct of research, view current research in a given area, including maps and publications, and make scientific and logistics support contacts.

Projected Activities

- Complete and test the development of database-rendered content display.
- Develop a “mailing list” of resource managers and other information sources.
- Solicit resource managers and identified users for logistics information input via electronic survey.
- Implement the dynamic display of the resulting content, via the database.
- Expand the above process into all planned coverage areas: Types of Platforms (Vessels, etc.), Data Resources, and Map resources.
- Address additional goals including:
 - Web site accessibility (ADA compliant version);
 - Additional web-based support for the research community, such as providing an online meeting space, information about funding opportunities, logistics bulletin boards for transportation and equipment sharing, research "classifieds", online request-response forum for information.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

During the past year, the focus of our efforts on the ALIAS project has shifted, as planned, from the initial task of implementing a static web resource, towards the long-term goal of a dynamic resource. While this has caused a reduction in the rate of visible progress on the existing static web site, it is crucial to the ultimate goals of the project. With the structure in place to dynamically receive and display logistics data from multiple sources around the world, ALIAS will have the capability to update in near-real time on a global scale.

1.3 Planning for Integrated Arctic Geographic Information Systems (GIS)

Accomplishments

- Convened 110 participants at a community workshop, in January 2001, to assess current capabilities and identify infrastructure and information needs for the use of GIS in arctic research and for research support.
- Published the Phase I report from the Arctic GIS Workshop, titled *Recommendations for a Geographic Information Infrastructure to Support Arctic Research: Outcomes of the Arctic GIS Workshop*, in April 2001, after several iterations of workshop participant and community review. The Phase I report presents a summary of workshop discussions and recommendations for the development of geographic information infrastructure to support arctic research
- Announced the availability of the Phase I report via Arctic Info and other relevant electronic lists and made it available electronically on the ARCUS web site.
- Requested review comments from workshop participants and other interested users and invited reviewers for use in the development of the final report.
- Assessed review comments and began development of the final report, to be published in hard copy in June 2002.

Projected Activities

- Completion and publication of the final report in June 2002. The final report will provide extensive community input to guide geographic information infrastructure development by NSF and other organizations.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

The publication of the final report was delayed from Fall 2001 to June 2002 because of personnel changes and other urgent project priorities.

1.4—1.6 Workshops, to be determined

Accomplishments

- No activities in the past year.

Projected Activities

- No activities are planned in the coming year

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

1.7 Revision and Reprinting of the SEARCH Brochure

Accomplishments

- Text and graphics were revised and minor layout changes made in the brochure for *SEARCH: The Study of Environmental Arctic Change*, originally published by

ARCUS for the SEARCH Interagency Working Group and the Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee in March 2001.

- 2,000 copies of the brochure were printed and all have been distributed.

Projected Activities

- No further activities are planned, although we receive many requests for the brochure and copies are no longer available.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

The revisions requested by the SEARCH Interagency Working Group were more significant than expected and required more staff time than was initially budgeted. Print costs increased slightly over the initial budget because a color proof was required to review proposed layout and color changes.

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

2.1 ARCTIC SECTION SCIENCE MATERIALS

Accomplishments

- Developed five interrelated posters on topics related to Arctic research for use by the NSF Arctic Section staff at scientific conferences and meetings.
- Conferred with NSF Arctic Section head, Tom Pyle, to identify topics, draft initial content, and develop layout ideas. The selected topics are:
 - Progress in Arctic Science
 - Arctic Research and Logistics Support
 - Long-term Observations
 - Technology in Arctic Science
 - Partnerships
- The posters' design and contents have been developed so that each stands on its own as an informational piece but any combination of the set can be used together effectively.
- Tom Pyle has reviewed the final drafts and final changes to the posters are pending.

Projected Activities

- Make final changes to the posters.
- Provide to the Arctic Section printed and laminated copies of the five posters in approximately 3 ft. by 4 ft. format.
- Provide PDFs of the posters to facilitate future printing.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

Completion of the posters was postponed until April 2002.

2.2 ARCTIC SYSTEM SCIENCE (ARCSS) PROGRAM COORDINATION

2.2.1 ARCSS Coordination

Accomplishments

- Worked with ARCSS Committee chair to prepare materials for several meetings of ARCSS Program science steering committees and other ARCSS investigators to assess the direction of the ARCSS Program, research priorities, new planning underway, the current funding picture, and important opportunities.
- Provided the committee chair with a stipend and travel funds to participate in ARCSS-related meetings and workshops.

- Convened a teleconference meeting of the ARCSS Committee, science steering committee chairs, science management office directors, and the NSF ARCSS Program Director in July 2001 to discuss new directions, planning within each component, and preparations for major upcoming meetings, including the joint OAI-LAI-RAISE-ITEX meeting in November 2001, and the February 2002 All-Hands Workshop.
- Assisted the ARCSS Committee chair with the development of materials, synthesis presentations, and communication processes to help ARCSS investigators identify important research findings, gaps in current understanding, and priorities for new ARCSS Program research.
- Convened a meeting of the ARCSS Committee in November 2001 with the ARCSS science steering committee chairs, science management office directors, and the NSF ARCSS Program Director, to continue the discussions about the future directions of the ARCSS Program and to plan for the 2nd ARCSS Program All-Hands Workshop and other activities to promote integration of ARCSS research.
- Worked with AC chair and committee members to prepare a proposal for an ARCSS Fellows program to promote the development of a cohort of Arctic modelers familiar with integrated research, and interdisciplinary perspectives.
- Recruited new ARCSS Committee chair, Jon Overpeck, to replace outgoing chair, Jack Kruse, who retired at the end of the ARCSS All-Hands Workshop, after five years in the position.
- Convened ARCSS Committee meeting at the end of the All-Hands Workshop to assess workshop discussions and recommendations and prepare synthesized information for distribution to the research community and recommendations to forward to the National Science Foundation.
- Provided general support for ARCSS science steering committees, science management offices, and lead researchers working on new initiatives, preparing and distributing information, graphics, and publications about ARCSS Program research upon request.

Projected Activities

- Convene a teleconference of the ARCSS Committee and new chair to review the recommendations from the All-Hands Workshop as well as from various ongoing planning efforts, and to discuss plans for the Committee's work over the next several years.
- Review the composition of the ARCSS Committee with the AC chair and the NSF Program Director in the context of new priorities and the representations of key programs and disciplinary perspectives and expertise.
- Select and appoint new members to replace members due to rotate off the committee.
- Convene a meeting of the ARCSS Committee in early Fall 2002.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

2.2.2 ARCSS All-Hands Workshop 2002

Accomplishments

- Worked with ARCSS Committee chair, committee members, and the ARCSS science management infrastructure to assess the progress made in the ARCSS Program in the past five years, and to identify key gaps and research priorities to formulate the agenda and key topics for the February 2002 All-Hands Workshop.
- Made evolving information and recommendations from these discussions available via the ARCUS web site.

- Worked with the ARCSS Committee chair to prepare a draft workshop agenda, which was then reviewed and revised during a twenty-eight –participant teleconference in July 2001.
- Prepared and posted background material and registration information for the workshop on the ARCUS web site. Developed an online abstract submission process and database so that all submitted abstracts could be viewed online.
- Distributed a broad community invitation to the ARCSS All-Hands Workshop, including a call for abstracts, via Arctic Info, other electronic lists, and the ARCUS web site.
- Worked with the ARCSS Committee chair, the ARCSS science management infrastructure, and the NSF ARCSS Program Director to prepare a database of all projects funded by the ARCSS Program, categorized by the ARCSS thematic focus, to identify gaps between research priorities identified in ARCSS Program science plans and the research actually funded and producing results.
- Worked with ARCSS science management infrastructure and ARCSS researchers to develop a list of ARCSS graduate and undergraduate students.
- Provided travel scholarships for student participation in the workshop. The eighty-seven students who received scholarships were required to present a poster at the workshop.
- Worked with the ARCSS science management infrastructure and ARCSS researchers to prepare materials about research initiatives in the planning stage and to host five online forums to engage the broader research community in discussions in the month prior to the workshop sessions, on:
 - Current ARCSS Research: Key Uncertainties and Next Steps
 - The pan-Arctic Community-wide Hydrological Analysis and Monitoring Program (Arctic-CHAMP)
 - The Nearshore and Coastal Processes Initiative
 - Modes of Variability in the Arctic System
 - Biophysical Feedbacks and Transitions in the Arctic Regional System.
- Refined the topics for breakout groups at the workshop and recruited facilitators for the groups.
- Posted final agenda, participant list, working group instructions, and other meeting information on the ARCUS web site and distributed it to all registered participants via email in advance of the meeting.
- Coordinated all arrangements for the workshop venue and the necessary technical and logistic support.
- Coordinated travel and participant arrangements for the workshop. Paid travel for invited speakers, ARCSS Committee members, and students, and paid for other meeting and support costs associated with the workshop.
- Prepared a draft compilation of the 176 abstracts submitted prior to the workshop for distribution and review at the workshop.
- Provided staff support for the four-day, 300-participant workshop. Participants represented 96 different institutions or organizations from six countries.
- Posted follow-up information on the ARCUS web site after the workshop, including PDF and Powerpoint downloads of all the presentations, a PDF of the online forum discussions, and poster and presentation abstracts.

Projected Activities

- Work with working group facilitators and presenters and the ARCSS Committee to synthesize recommendations from the workshop and make them available to the research community online for comment.
- Prepare and publish the proceedings from the workshop, including presentation and poster abstracts, a summary of the recommendations from each working group, and

the ARCSS Committee's analysis and synthesis of recommendations for further planning and implementation of ARCSS Program priorities.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

The ARCSS Committee recommended in November 2001 that travel support be provided for student participation in the All-Hands Workshop. The NSF-ARCSS Program Director concurred. This decision increased ARCUS' costs for participant support for the workshop and required more staff time to create and manage a student scholarship program and additional staff time to make travel and lodging arrangements for over eighty students that participated.

2.2.3 Coordinating a Human Dimensions of the Arctic System (HARC) Science Management Office

Accomplishments

- Established the HARC Science Management Office (SMO) in August 2001.
- Developed a HARC web site <<http://www.arcus.org/harc>>, including a description of the role of the science management office, background information about the HARC research initiative, research currently funded by the program, a downloadable PDF of the original prospectus for the HARC research initiative, and useful links and contacts.
- Planned and implemented three online workshops in Fall 2001 to engage the broader and multi-disciplinary research community in discussions related to potential HARC research. Each workshop was announced via Arctic Info and a special invitation was sent to individuals identified by their disciplinary and research interests in the Directory of Arctic Researchers.
- The online workshops were:
 - Arctic Weather: Implications of changing weather patterns in the Arctic
 - Northern Treeline: The location of the arctic treeline and its implications for humans
 - Ice: Effects of sea ice changes on coastal communities
- Provided for each workshop via the HARC web site background information about the HARC initiative, biographical information about the workshop moderators, relevant reference materials, online registration, participant lists, and access to and instructions for the online forum.
- Prepared daily summaries of the online forum discussions, distributed them to registered participants, and posted the summaries online each day of the workshop.
- Prepared final reports in PDF summarizing the discussions and recommendations from each online workshop, distributed the reports to all registered participants, and announced the availability of the reports to the broader research community via Arctic Info. All reports are also available for downloading from the HARC web site.
- Assisted the HARC SMO director, Henry Huntington, in preparing for presentations on HARC research at the ARCSS All-Hands Workshop in February 2002 and for a special session at the Arctic Workshop in March 2002.
- Scheduled and facilitated meetings of HARC principal investigators and other interested researchers at the ARCSS All-Hands Workshop in February 2002 and the Arctic Workshop in March 2002.

Projected Activities

- Plan and implement a series of online workshops in Spring 2002 focused on developing HARC proposals for new and emerging research initiatives. The first online workshop will focus on HARC integration with CHAMP, the second will focus on integration with the Nearshore and Coastal Processes initiative, and a third workshop may address SEARCH.

- Refine HARC web site to include information about additional HARC and HARC-like research projects.
- Arrange for HARC special issue of the journal ARCTIC. Solicit contributions from funded HARC researchers.
- Facilitate HARC workshop at the Center for Global Change and Arctic System research at the University of Alaska Fairbanks in April 2002.
- Convene HARC All-Hands Workshop in Fall 2002.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

2.2.4 Preparation and publication of CHAMP: *The Hydrologic Cycle and its Role in Arctic and Global Environmental Change: A Rationale and Strategy for Synthesis Study*

Accomplishments

- Coordinated with workshop participants and co-chairs to outline report contents and draft sections of the report.
- Edited draft text and prepared preliminary report layout and distributed to workshop participants for review.
- Integrated review comments prepared draft for community review. The report was made available for review via the ARCUS web site and printed copies were mailed on request.
- Community review comments were integrated, and final graphics and final figures obtained or created.
- The final report was reviewed by co-chairs and invited reviewers and comments integrated.
- The report was published and distributed by ARCUS, including printed copies and electronically via the ARCUS web site. The University of New Hampshire, however, paid the printing cost for 1,300 copies of the report, using funds remaining from support for the initial planning workshop.
- Prepared a poster summarizing the report's recommendations for use at several scientific meetings.
- Prepared a Powerpoint presentation summarizing the report's recommendations for use by the workshop co-chairs and other participants to provide information to the research community at scientific meetings.

Projected Activities

- Ongoing distribution of the report, including printed copies and electronically via the ARCUS web site.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

2.3 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION

2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Community Conference

Accomplishments

- Worked with the Arctic Social Sciences Workshop organizing committee members to summarize and synthesize the recommendations from the January 2001 planning workshop.

- Solicited comments on the needs and priorities in arctic social sciences from the participants at the International Congress of Arctic Social Sciences held in Quebec City, Canada in May 2001, the May 2001 Arctic Forum.
- Posted summaries and recommendations on ARCUS web site.

Projected Activities

- Discuss conference focus, goals, and timing with the NSF Arctic Social Sciences Program Manager.
- Select and convene a conference organizing committee.
- Identify timeline, main topics, keynote speakers, and invited participants.
- Announce the conference and publish a call for abstracts.
- Convene the conference in early 2003, bringing academic arctic researchers together with social scientists based in other regions, federal and state agency scientists, and policy and decision-makers working on related issues. The conference format will include sessions on a variety of topics, panel discussions, and a poster session, with ample opportunities for brainstorming and informal discussions.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

2.3.2 Translation and publication of *Den Nye Sikkerhed - Groenland I Et Sikkerhedspolitisk Perspektiv* (The New Security: Greenland in a Security Political Perspective)

ARCUS coordinated planning for the preparation and publication of *Grønland i et Sikkerhedspolitisk Perspektiv* (*Greenland in a Security Policy Perspective*), written by Jørgen Taagholt and Jens Claus Hansen with funds from the previous cooperative agreement with NSF. This study initially appeared in 1999 as part of the Danish Atlantic Treaty Association's series *Den Nye Sikkerhed* (The New Security). The authors emphasized Greenland's role during the Cold War and the future security policy implications of Greenland. This book is an English translation of that study and there have been modifications by the authors to this version.

Accomplishments

- Received translated text and prepared the book layout and edited text to fit.
- Identified or prepared appropriate graphics for the publication.
- The book was reviewed by the co-authors, the translator, and several invited reviewers.
- The book was published with 1,780 copies printed, and copies were made available in time for presentation at a March 2001 Security Political Seminar in Nuuk/Godthaab, Greenland.
- The publication is available electronically on the ARCUS web site and printed copies are available by request.
- Copies of the publication have been made available at a number of political science or social sciences workshops, by request.

Projected Activities

- Ongoing distribution of *Grønland i et Sikkerhedspolitisk Perspektiv* at meetings, workshops, and by request.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

2.3.3 Preparation and Publication of *The Earth is Faster Now: Indigenous Observations of Arctic Environmental Change*

Accomplishments

- Discussed with the editors the probable size of the volume, the number of papers to be contributed, the publication timeline, illustrations and graphics, and the general layout requirements.
- Completed the design of the publication.
- Received all of the invited papers, including illustrations.
- Prepared first draft of several chapters in layout.
- Selected art and designed the cover.
- Requested estimates from three printers and selected best.

Projected Activities

- Complete layout and proofreading.
- Send to editors and authors for review.
- Publish the volume in time for distribution at the ARCUS Annual Meeting and Arctic Forum in May 2002.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

2.4 ARCTIC NATURAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION

2.4.1 Arctic Natural Sciences Program Materials

Accomplishments

- No activities in the past year.

Projected Activities

- No activities planned in the coming year.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities

Accomplishments

- Participated in a collaborative arctic science education project, *Eider Journey*, which provides research experiences for arctic students and teachers, in collaboration with several federal agencies and arctic communities. This interdisciplinary and multi-agency collaboration included the Alaska North Slope Borough (NSB) Department of Wildlife Management (DWM), the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS), Izembek Refuge, schools in Cold Bay, Alaska, the NSB School District, and faculty from the University of Alaska Fairbanks, along with ARCUS.

Through these local partnerships, an education program has been developed that reflects local needs and community issues. *Eider Journey* encourages students, teachers, and community members to understand their local environment and provides a basis of knowledge from which they can make informed decisions. The project engages both students and teachers in scientific research and provides training on field methods, analysis, and hypothesis testing. Activities initiated and supported by ARCUS include coordination of teacher and student participation with the research project and assistance in the

development of educational materials. The collaborative work on *Eider Journey* also made possible funding from the National Fish and Wildlife Foundation to develop an educator's guide that will be used to support this and other arctic science education projects.

- Provided scientific and educational contacts for *Shaping Vocational Frontiers: Science, Engineering and Mathematics for Persons with Disabilities in Rural and Remote Areas*, a project conducted by the University of Hawaii and Access Alaska and funded by NSF Education and Human Resources (EHR).
- Worked with the Alaska Federation of Natives (AFN), the Alaska Native Knowledge Network (ANKN), and the University of Alaska Fairbanks in collaboration with the NSF-funded Rural Systemic Initiative (RSI), to compile integrated curricular materials and to make them available to a wide national audience and to provide technical assistance and training to RSI participants in Alaskan communities.
- Continued working with Arctic Native organizations and scientists to develop effective means by which the results of NSF-funded research can be returned to northern communities. ARCUS continues to develop relationships, resources, and expertise in this area. One example of planning at this level was ARCUS staff participation in the Education working group at the April 2001 Barrow facilities planning workshop in Barrow, Alaska.
- Provided information and recommendations to the JASON Project IV–Frozen Worlds. Recommended and helped facilitate contact with NSF-funded investigators to work with and provide information to teachers about the Arctic.
- Prepared a four-page insert to *Witness the Arctic* providing information and advice to researchers on developing appropriate and useful science education projects, including information about education on global climate change, indigenous knowledge, and tips on bringing research into the classroom.
- Continued to support and promote the development and successful implementation of arctic science education projects by sharing information and expertise, supporting communicative networks, and distributing information about results and opportunities.

Projected Activities

- Present information about science education projects and opportunities at research community seminars, such as the University of Alaska –Center for Global Change information series.
- Provide curriculum materials from arctic science education projects, such as Arctic Alive and the *Eider Journey* education guide, to Eisenhower Clearinghouse (<http://enc.org>) for access by more educators around the US.
- Submit articles about arctic science education for publication to professional and refereed journals (i.e. *Eider Journey* to Clearing Magazine, an educational magazine for the Pacific Northwest, as well as the Canadian Journal of Environmental Education, a refereed journal on environmental education).
- Provide information to and possibly participate in advisory committees associated with grantees awarded for the NSF “Math and Science Partnership (MSP) Program.”
- Present information on arctic research, education, and information resources offered by the National Science Foundation through ARCUS at GLOBE summer trainings, in Alaska, and potentially throughout the U.S.
- Expand the *Eider Journey* Educator's Guide to include lessons and background material focused on the North Slope of Alaska natural history, coastal ecosystems, and other aspects of the North Slope environment. Includes curriculum development and design work for publication of guide.
- Professional development for the ARCUS education project manager to attend a National Educational Computing Association (NECA) annual conference.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series

ARCUS implemented an Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series in January 2000 to increase communication and collaboration among the dispersed arctic research community and to nurture better understanding and communication between arctic researchers and arctic community residents.

Accomplishments

- Advertised the Series on-line, at meetings, and through *Witness the Arctic*.
- From April 2001 to March 2002, eleven speakers addressed audiences at twenty-seven institutions at graduate and undergraduate university seminars, presentations in K-12 schools, and presentations open to the public.
- Speakers covered arctic research topics in the disciplines of anthropology, archaeology, climate data, contaminants in the arctic, geology, linguistics, international law, oral history, traditional healing, and general arctic research in the program.
- Four speakers traveled from other countries to speak in the U.S.; three U.S. researchers traveled to other countries. Four U.S. speakers visited institutions within the U.S.

Projected Activities

- Continue to promote the use of the Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series to promote collaboration and information sharing about arctic research and the Arctic.
- Support between ten and fifteen speaker tours in the next year.
- Continue to recruit individuals for the Speakers Bureau, although host institutions are not restricted to inviting speakers from the Speakers' Bureau.
- Post updated information about speaker tours on the ARCUS web site, including presentation videos and other materials sent to ARCUS by host institutions and speakers.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

3.3 Arctic Science Education Report

ARCUS convened a 15-member working group of selected researchers, educators, students, and arctic community representatives in March 2000 to review various programs and educational approaches to science education and to prepare recommendations for the development of research-experience-based science education programs for the Arctic. The previous ARCUS cooperative agreement funded development of the report and circulation of the draft for community review.

Accomplishments

- Completed and published the report based on contributions and comments from reviewers.

Projected Activities

- Distribute 600 copies and make the report and its recommendations available electronically through the ARCUS web site.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

4.1 *Witness the Arctic*: Chronicles of the Arctic Science Research Program

Accomplishments

- Published and distributed 7,200 copies of a 28-page issue of *Witness* in May 2001 (Winter 2000/2001, Volume 8, Number 2) plus a four-page insert featuring the Norwegian Polar Institute. The newsletter feature story was titled “Ozone Losses Increase Possible UV Impacts in the Arctic.”
- Published and distributed 7,750 copies of a 28-page issue of *Witness* in October 2001 (Autumn 2001, Volume 9, Number 1) plus a four-page Special Science Education Supplement, a four-page Arctic Section and ARCSS Program address insert, and a four-page ARCUS address insert. The newsletter feature story was titled “SCICEX Sonars Chart New Topographies, New Theories.”
- Published on-line editions of the newsletters on ARCUS’ web site, <http://www.arcus.org>.
- Began work on the next issue of *Witness* (Spring 2002, Volume 9, Number 2). This issue is planned as a 28-page newsletter, plus a four-page insert on arctic research at Louisiana State University, a four-page Arctic Section and ARCSS address insert, and a four-page ARCUS address insert.

Projected Activities

- Publish and distribute 8,000 copies of Spring 2002 (Volume 9, Number 2) issue of *Witness the Arctic*.
- Prepare, publish, and distribute over 8,300 copies of a 40-page issue of *Witness* in October 2002 (Autumn 2002, Volume 10, Number 1). Publish on-line edition of the newsletter on ARCUS’ web site, <http://www.arcus.org>.
- Begin work on Spring 2003 issue of *Witness* (Volume 10, Number 1), which will be published in May 2003.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

The number of newsletter subscribers continues to increase with each issue, with commensurate increases in printing and distribution costs. We plan to use a new distribution method for the issue now in process, which we hope will offset the additional costs related to increased subscribers.

4.2 Web Site/Internet Resources

Accomplishments

- Continuous development and maintenance of the over 5,000-page ARCUS web site to provide:
 - Sources of information for the general public about arctic research.
 - A forum for scientific exchange among arctic researchers.
 - Suggestions for integration into educational programs.
 - Access to other researchers, programs, and stakeholders working in the Arctic.
 - Viable ways to inform and involve arctic residents in research activities.
 - Information about progress and recommendations related to various arctic research initiatives, including projects coordinated by ARCUS as well as other organizations.
- Posted draft reports related to arctic research activities, making them available for community review.
- Posted on-line versions of various arctic research publications, including all documents prepared by ARCUS, for easy access and downloading.

- Created, maintained, and updated sections of the web site for various ARCUS-facilitated programs, meetings and workshops as mentioned under other activity descriptions in this report.
- Provided links to numerous other arctic organizations' research sites, databases, planning processes, and other information of interest to the arctic research community.
- Provided support and consultation for the development of Internet resources by other institutions and organizations working with arctic research or arctic science education.

Projected Activities

- Initiate a major redesign of several sections of the web site to improve search functions, information delivery, and ease of information management, including the general education site, the Arctic Visiting Speakers' site, and the publication download section.
- Initiate a major redesign of the interface and database backbone for the Directory of Arctic Researchers, the Calendar, Arctic Info, and Hot Links to resolve problems in the database code, improve search capability and speed, and to update the user interface.
- Continue to maintain, manage, and update this monster of a web site.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

Continuation and upgrading of activities in response to community needs and requests from researchers, various organizations, federal and Alaska state agencies, and the National Science Foundation. This gradual increase in the level of use and the kind of information made available on the site has required increasingly sophisticated technology—hardware and software—and additional time and technical expertise.

4.3 Arctic Info Listserve

Accomplishments

- Received, reviewed, accepted or declined, edited, and formatted over 450 submissions for the Arctic Info listserv in the past year.
- Communicated with subscribers regarding postings, special information requests, non-automated subscribe or unsubscribe requests, and other concerns.
- Upgraded the Arctic Info server to a faster machine to expedite the handling of the expanding subscriber list and multiple message postings per day.
- Maintained database of subscribers in order to analyze use and areas of interest.
- Distributed 315 Arctic Info messages from the beginning of this cooperative agreement through March 2002.
- The listserv has 3,855 current subscribers, an increase of over 600 subscribers in the past year.

Projected Activities

- Continue advertising, maintenance, and management of the listserv. Switch from current listserv software to a more user friendly, less annoying and anxiety provoking list management software.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

4.4 The Directory of Arctic Researchers

Accomplishments

- Added new records for a total of 3,500 as of March 2002.
- Switched the Directory server to a more powerful computer to increase the speed and accessibility of the on-line directory.
- Maintained and regularly updated a downloadable PDF of the Directory including alphabetically listed individual researcher entries and a cross-reference file listing researchers by name within science specialty categories.
- Provided subsets of directory information in response to requests from the Canadian Polar Commission, the International Glaciological Society, the University Corporation for Atmospheric Research, and the Global Hydrology and Climate Center.

Projected Activities

- Continuing maintenance and expansion of the on-line version of the directory. A database expansion is underway to include arctic science administrators at Alaska State agencies, federal agencies, and significant international research organizations.
- Upgrades of hardware and software to keep pace with information technology improvements.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

4.5 Internet Graphics Archive

Accomplishments

- No activities in the current year.

Projected Activities

- Identify or produce figures, cartoons, photographs, and maps depicting arctic research-related information and make this information available through the archive on the ARCUS Web site.
- Continue to develop short abstracts that explain each graphic simply and clearly and that provide information necessary for attribution, as well as citations for source material and other related references.
- Make graphics available for downloading and printing from the ARCUS Web site through a searchable database and PDF format.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

4.6 Arctic Community Outreach

Accomplishments

- Planned and hosted a two-day *Arctic Forum* in conjunction with ARCUS' 13th Annual Meeting in Arlington, VA in May 2001, attended by 107 participants, including arctic researchers from the U.S. and other countries, policy makers, federal agency personnel, and Arctic residents. The *Forum* focused on interactions between the biological and physical systems.
- The *Arctic Forum* in 2001 featured forty-seven arctic research projects in oral and poster presentations, including projects funded by NSF, arctic research supported

by other federal agencies or programs, and significant international arctic research efforts.

- Printed and distributed 750 copies of the proceedings from the 2001 *Arctic Forum*.
- Developed information resources regarding arctic research activities, needs, and priorities and participated in outreach activities at scientific meetings and workshops to inform the broader scientific community and key policy and decisions-makers about important arctic research efforts and findings.

Projected Activities

- Convene two-day *Arctic Forum* in conjunction with ARCUS' 14th Annual Meeting in Arlington, VA in May 2002. Dr. Rita Colwell, Director of NSF, will be the keynote speaker at the *Arctic Forum 2002*, which will focus on Biocomplexity in the Arctic.
- Print and distribute the *Arctic Forum 2002* abstract volume.
- Prepare posters or presentations on request and participate in major scientific meetings or workshops to provide information and outreach regarding arctic research activities, needs, and priorities.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

4.7 Publication: The Arctic

Many members of the arctic research community have expressed a need for an introduction to the environments and peoples of the Arctic that is scientifically accurate while remaining comprehensible to the general public, including middle and high school students. To address this need, ARCUS began developing an overview of the arctic region for a general audience in 2001, with funding through the previous cooperative agreement with NSF. Tentatively titled *The Arctic: Changes in a Polar Region*, this book is similar to a magazine in the quality of graphics and level of complexity and will be accessible to a wide range of readers. The contents and the publication design and layout are targeted to the general public and middle and high school students. The contents cover ocean, terrestrial, and human components of the Arctic and review various aspects of these domains, including contemporary and historical research, through a seasonal framework. Links among important arctic processes and between the biophysical systems and human cultures are illustrated.

Accomplishments

- In January 2001 the draft publication was circulated for review by a group of educators, arctic researchers, and experts in science information development. The reviews provided substantive guidance for the difficult task of describing diverse and complex processes simply and clearly.

Projected Activities

- Integrate reviewer 's comments and reorganize and rewrite several significant sections of the publication.
- Research and purchase photo rights for photos selected for the final publication.
- Prepare final versions of special graphics for publication.
- Publish in December 2002 and make the initial print run of 5,000 copies available for public information requests and educational uses. The publication also will be available electronically via the ARCUS web site.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

Because of the amount of work still required to create a publication of the quality considered necessary by ARCUS, NSF, and the research community, we have

postponed further work on this publication to the latter half of the second year of the cooperative agreement in order to direct staff resources to other more urgently needed projects.

4.8 Eider Endangered Species Consultation Bulletin

Accomplishments

- Met with U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) staff to discuss the requirements for consultation with USFWS regarding potential impacts of research on listed species and to gather information about the consultation process.
- Researched the Endangered Species Act and the requirement that Federal agencies consult with USFWS.
- Compiled background materials on the two species of sea duck that may be affected by activities associated with scientific research on the North Slope of Alaska, the spectacled eider (*Somateria fischeri*) and Steller's eider (*Polysticta stelleri*).
- Prepared the layout and contents for a draft consultation bulletin informing researchers about the species in question, the critical time periods, and geographic areas of concern, including maps and photos.
- Designed a questionnaire to guide researchers and NSF program managers through a decision-making process to determine what level of consultation is required, how to initiate the consultation process, and who to contact for further information.
- The draft consultation bulletin was reviewed and approved by USFWS staff in the Endangered Species Division and was also sent to the Alaska North Slope Borough Department of Wildlife Management and the Barrow Arctic Science Consortium for review and comment.
- The consultation bulletin was forwarded to NSF Arctic Section for discussion.

Projected Activities

- When the process is determined and the consultation bulletin finally approved, copies will be made available as a downloadable PDF linked from various web sites providing research support and logistics information to arctic researchers, as well as being available as a photocopied handout.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

5. Core Support

Core support provides management and infrastructure crucial to support all major tasks and the projects and activities included in each task through the cooperative agreement. This category was initiated at the recommendation of the NSF program officer, who suggested that stability and continuity would be achieved more effectively by defining a category to support direct activities that support the whole of the cooperative agreement that would not be vulnerable to the changes in the specific tasks and activities funded from year-to-year through the cooperative agreement.

ARCUS is a relatively small non-profit organization and the Executive Director is intimately involved in all activities of the organization including planning, prioritizing, managing, and directly implementing the work undertaken on behalf of the National Science Foundation. The Executive Director works closely with ARCUS project managers to prioritize tasks with respect to annual and longer-term plans and to manage individual workloads and projects. She closely reviews activities and products and ensures that projects are completed as scheduled and in accordance with the annual plan and that the products or effects of the activities are beneficial to arctic research and to the goals of the particular task funded through the cooperative agreement.

She is directly involved in working with outside committees and contributors to ensure that projects are concluded effectively and in a timely fashion. The Executive Director also works closely with the ARCUS Business Manager in budgeting and reviewing ongoing project expenditures against the NSF budget. The Executive Director liaises directly with NSF on all planning, programmatic, and budget issues. This component of management is essential to the ongoing work ARCUS carries out on behalf of NSF.

Similarly, the Systems Administrator manages the network, server, and all technical needs required to support NSF tasks and sub-tasks. He works directly with the Executive Director to ensure that all hardware and software requirements are met so that server and network operations supporting NSF activities are carried out smoothly and efficiently. The Executive Director and Systems Administrator research and plan for upcoming needs, including scientific meetings and conferences convened by ARCUS on behalf of the NSF, in conjunction with the annual plan.

While the work of both these positions is directly related to the successful implementation of NSF activities and projects, it is more difficult to allocate much of this time specifically to any one individual project, hence the use of Core Support to collect these direct overarching management and infrastructure costs. Other costs charged to Core Support include direct system infrastructure (computer hardware and software required to maintain the network and server needed to support the database and listserver, NSF sponsored tasks), high-speed Internet lines, and the development necessary to continuously maintain the level of service committed to the Arctic research community under the cooperative agreement.

Accomplishments

- Coordinated planning, managed emerging priorities, and supervised work on all the tasks and sub-tasks described in this report. The portion of the Executive Director's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement is charged to the Core Support category.
- Upgraded hardware, software, and programming to expand capability for several projects that require expanded server, network, and database capacity, including the Directory of Arctic Researchers, the ALIAS web site, Arctic Info, the Calendar, and support for NSF-sponsored meeting online registration, poster submission, and general information.
- Managed the server setup, the network, the creation of needed technical resources, and the computing capability that directly supports the project activities. The portion of the System Administrator's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement is charged to the Core Support category.
- Supported staff training to increase technical expertise for programming and managing database backbone for all database-driven functions of the ARCUS web site, which serves the Directory of Arctic Researchers, the ALIAS web site, Arctic Info, the Calendar, and support for NSF-sponsored meeting online registration, poster submission, and general information.
- Supported staff travel to arctic research meetings and workshops that addressed topics pertaining to multiple NSF projects and activities included in the cooperative agreement, but which were not specific to one project.

Projected Activities

- Coordinate planning, prioritization and supervision of work on all the tasks and projects described in the program plan for 2002-2003. The portion of the Executive Director's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement will be charged to the Core Support category.
- Continue to research and upgrade hardware, software and programming required to expand the capability of such projects as the Directory of Arctic Researchers, the

- ALIAS website, Arctic Info, the Calendar and NSF online program discussions, meeting registrations and poster submissions, and general information.
- Manage the server setup, the network, the creation of needed technical resources, and the computing capability that directly supports the project activities. The portion of the System Administrator's time dedicated to direct activities funded through this agreement will be charged to the Core Support category.
 - Support staff participation at arctic research meetings and workshops on topics pertaining to multiple NSF projects and activities included in the cooperative agreement, but which are not specific to one project.

Significant Changes in Direction or Pace

None

Total Costs by Category

	5-year Budget	Year 1 Budget	YEAR 1 Thru 3/31/02	Funds Remaining (Shortfall)	PROPOSED Year 2 Budget
1 ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING					
1.1 Arctic Logistics	388,437	51,585	19,366	32,219	83,658
1.2 ALIAS Website	480,011	101,180	98,219	2,961	114,731
1.3 GIS Planning	50,082	51,566	35,469	16,097	32,268
1.4 Workshop TBD	64,915	-	-	-	-
1.5 Workshop TBD	66,304	-	-	-	-
1.6 Workshop TBD	67,846	-	-	-	-
1.7 SEARCH Brochure	-	4,421	5,736	(1,315)	-
SubTotal Direct Costs	1,117,593	208,752	158,791	49,961	230,657
Indirect Costs	470,507	87,885	66,978	20,906	97,107
TOTAL	1,588,100	296,637	225,770	70,867	327,764
2 NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION					
2.1 Arctic Section Science Materials	24,782	24,763	7,095	17,668	17,613
2.2 ARCSS Program Coordination					
2.2.1 ARCSS Coordination	225,670	37,251	31,472	5,779	101,221
2.2.2 ARCSS All-Hands	147,106	313,706	273,595	40,111	37,885
2.2.3 HARC SMO	151,980	51,831	52,177	(346)	50,856
2.2.4 Arctic Hydrology Report	11,543	17,002	18,256	(1,254)	-
SubTotal 2.2 Direct Costs	536,299	419,790	375,501	44,289	189,961
2.3 ASSP Program Coordination					
2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Workshop	64,060	8,583	6,472	2,111	64,834
2.3.2 Greenland Book	19,543	12,264	12,263	1	-
2.3.3 Arctic Social Sciences Volume	-	42,319	13,155	29,164	31,162
SubTotal 2.3 Direct Costs	83,602	63,166	31,889	31,277	95,996
2.4 ANS Program Coordination					
2.4.1 ANS materials	18,493	-	-	-	-
Sub-Total Direct Costs	663,176	507,719	414,485	93,234	303,569
Indirect Costs	279,197	213,750	174,830	38,920	127,802
TOTAL	942,373	721,469	589,314	132,155	431,371
3 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION					
3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities	75,444	11,388	10,966	422	14,963
3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers Program	175,681	36,965	36,201	764	38,441
3.3 Arctic Science Education Report	-	27,578	26,068	1,510	-
SubTotal Direct Costs	251,125	75,931	73,235	2,696	53,404
Indirect Costs	105,724	31,967	30,890	1,076	22,483
TOTAL	356,849	107,898	104,125	3,773	75,887
4 INFORMATION AND OUTREACH					
4.1 Witness the Arctic Newsletter	302,879	60,581	53,255	7,326	77,914
4.2 Web Site/Internet Resources	372,565	66,876	68,542	(1,666)	67,024
4.3 Arctic Info Listserver	98,790	16,275	12,507	3,768	16,686
4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers	39,305	11,632	16,321	(4,689)	12,446
4.5 Internet Graphics Archive	63,750	-	-	-	15,250
4.6 Community Outreach	208,890	45,931	47,711	(1,780)	51,427
4.7 Publication: The Arctic	-	58,113	867	57,246	43,515
4.8 Endangered Species Consultation Bulletin	-	1,782	2,245	(463)	-
SubTotal Direct Costs	1,086,179	261,190	201,449	59,740	284,262
Indirect Costs	457,281	94,917	84,971	9,946	112,622
TOTAL	1,543,460	356,107	286,421	69,686	396,884
5 CORE SUPPORT					
SubTotal Direct Costs	1,426,996	233,562	267,267	(33,705)	315,971
Indirect Costs	600,765	98,330	112,733	(14,404)	133,024
TOTAL	2,027,761	331,892	380,000	(48,108)	448,995
TOTAL COSTS	6,458,543	1,814,002	1,585,629	228,372	1,680,900

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
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NSF Task Summary

	<u>5-year Budget</u>	<u>Year 1 Budget</u>	<u>YEAR 1 Thru 3/31/02</u>	<u>Funds Remaining (Shortfall)</u>	<u>Proposed Year 2 Budget</u>
1 Arctic Community Science Planning					
1.1 ARCTIC LOGISTICS					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	109,509	25,428	9,789	15,639	22,815
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	32,140	4,143	4,127	16	6,308
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	165,620	14,354	2,634	11,720	27,100
Other Direct Costs	<u>81,168</u>	<u>7,660</u>	<u>2,817</u>	<u>4,843</u>	<u>27,435</u>
Total direct costs	388,437	51,585	19,366	32,219	83,658
Indirect Costs	<u>163,532</u>	<u>21,717</u>	<u>8,169</u>	<u>13,549</u>	<u>35,220</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>551,968</u>	<u>73,302</u>	<u>27,535</u>	<u>45,767</u>	<u>118,878</u>
1.2 ALIAS WEBSITE					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	387,761	64,424	61,366	3,058	79,461
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	80,350	14,952	14,187	765	15,770
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	<u>11,900</u>	<u>21,804</u>	<u>22,666</u>	<u>(862)</u>	<u>19,500</u>
Total direct costs	480,011	101,180	98,219	2,961	114,731
Indirect Costs	<u>202,084</u>	<u>42,597</u>	<u>41,429</u>	<u>1,168</u>	<u>48,302</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>682,095</u>	<u>143,777</u>	<u>139,648</u>	<u>4,129</u>	<u>163,033</u>
1.3 GIS PLANNING					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	13,282	18,434	20,929	(2,495)	4,968
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	631	2,294	(1,663)	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	7,000	8,050	8,050	(0)	-
Other Direct Costs	<u>29,800</u>	<u>24,451</u>	<u>4,196</u>	<u>20,255</u>	<u>27,300</u>
Total direct costs	50,082	51,566	35,469	16,097	32,268
Indirect Costs	<u>21,084</u>	<u>21,709</u>	<u>14,961</u>	<u>6,748</u>	<u>13,585</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>71,166</u>	<u>73,275</u>	<u>50,430</u>	<u>22,845</u>	<u>45,853</u>
1.4 WKSP TBD					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	16,536	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic and foreign)	3,204	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	31,725	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	<u>13,450</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct costs	64,915	-	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	<u>27,329</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>92,244</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
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NSF Task Summary

	<u>5-year Budget</u>	<u>Year 1 Budget</u>	<u>YEAR 1 Thru 3/31/02</u>	<u>Funds Remaining (Shortfall)</u>	<u>Proposed Year 2 Budget</u>
1.5 WKSP TBD					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	17,250	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	3,254	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	32,350	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	13,450	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	<u>66,304</u>	-	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	27,914	-	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>94,218</u>	-	-	-	-

1.6 WKSP TBD					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	18,117	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	3,304	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	32,975	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	13,450	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	<u>67,846</u>	-	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	28,563	-	-	-	-
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>96,409</u>	-	-	-	-

1.7 SEARCH BROCHURE					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	1,085	1,085	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	3,336	4,652	(1,316)	-
Total direct costs	-	4,421	5,736	(1,315)	-
Indirect Costs	-	1,861	2,420	(558)	-
Total direct and indirect costs	-	6,282	8,156	(1,874)	-

2 NSF Arctic Sciences Section Coordination

2.1 ARCTIC SECTION SCIENCE MATERIALS

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	13,282	13,263	6,854	6,409	9,113
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	11,500	11,500	241	11,259	8,500
Total direct costs	<u>24,782</u>	<u>24,763</u>	<u>7,095</u>	<u>17,668</u>	<u>17,613</u>
Indirect Costs	10,433	10,425	2,993	7,433	7,415
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>35,215</u>	<u>35,188</u>	<u>10,088</u>	<u>25,100</u>	<u>25,027</u>

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2.2 ARCSS PROGRAM COORDINATION					
2.2.1 ARCSS COORDINATION					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	60,200	11,045	9,399	1,646	28,553
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	28,124	4,731	4,244	487	5,520
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	119,250	16,985	10,677	6,308	13,550
Other Direct Costs	18,096	4,490	7,151	(2,661)	53,598
Total direct costs	225,670	37,251	31,472	5,779	101,221
Indirect Costs	95,007	15,683	13,275	2,408	42,614
Total direct and indirect costs	320,677	52,934	44,746	8,187	143,834
2.2.2 ARCSS ALL-HANDS WORKSHOP					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	62,023	33,596	47,754	(14,158)	14,270
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	6,308	16,970	15,237	1,733	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	47,425	154,340	85,703	68,637	1,355
Other Direct Costs	31,350	108,800	124,901	(16,101)	22,260
Total direct costs	147,106	313,706	273,595	40,111	37,885
Indirect Costs	61,932	132,070	115,402	16,668	15,949
Total direct and indirect costs	209,037	445,776	388,998	56,778	53,834
2.2.3 HARC SMO					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	31,957	21,671	20,303	1,368	10,949
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	14,268	4,896	5,249	(353)	4,731
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	39,807	2,932	2,932	-	13,194
Other Direct Costs	65,948	22,332	23,693	(1,361)	21,982
Total direct costs	151,980	51,831	52,177	(346)	50,856
Indirect Costs	63,984	21,821	22,008	(188)	21,410
Total direct and indirect costs	215,964	73,652	74,186	(534)	72,266
2.2.4 ARCTIC HYDROLOGY REPORT					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	9,775	15,796	16,279	(483)	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	1,768	1,206	1,977	(771)	-
Total direct costs	11,543	17,002	18,256	(1,254)	-
Indirect Costs	4,859	7,158	7,701	(543)	-
Total direct and indirect costs	16,402	24,160	25,957	(1,797)	-

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2.3 <i>ASSP PROGRAM COORDINATION</i>					
2.3.1 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES WORKSHOP					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	15,822	8,524	6,172	2,352	16,596
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	3,154	46	46	(0)	3,154
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	31,100	-	-	-	31,100
Other Direct Costs	<u>13,984</u>	<u>13</u>	<u>254</u>	<u>(241)</u>	<u>13,984</u>
Total direct costs	64,060	8,583	6,472	2,111	64,834
Indirect Costs	<u>26,969</u>	<u>3,613</u>	<u>2,730</u>	<u>884</u>	<u>27,295</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u><u>91,029</u></u>	<u><u>12,196</u></u>	<u><u>9,201</u></u>	<u><u>2,995</u></u>	<u><u>92,128</u></u>
2.3.2 GREENLAND BOOK					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	6,043	1,327	1,326	1	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	<u>13,500</u>	<u>10,937</u>	<u>10,937</u>	<u>(0)</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct costs	19,543	12,264	12,263	1	-
Indirect Costs	<u>8,228</u>	<u>5,163</u>	<u>5,172</u>	<u>(9)</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u><u>27,771</u></u>	<u><u>17,427</u></u>	<u><u>17,435</u></u>	<u><u>(8)</u></u>	<u><u>-</u></u>
2.3.3 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES VOLUME					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	6,501	2,155	4,346	6,345
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	1,577	-	1,577	1,577
Travel (foreign)	-	3,549	-	3,549	3,548
Participant Support Costs	-	13,000	11,000	2,000	2,000
Other Direct Costs	<u>-</u>	<u>17,692</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>17,692</u>	<u>17,692</u>
Total direct costs	-	42,319	13,155	29,164	31,162
Indirect Costs	<u>-</u>	<u>17,816</u>	<u>5,549</u>	<u>12,268</u>	<u>13,119</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u><u>-</u></u>	<u><u>60,135</u></u>	<u><u>18,703</u></u>	<u><u>41,432</u></u>	<u><u>44,281</u></u>
2.4 <i>ANS PROGRAM COORDINATION</i>					
2.4.1 ANS MATERIALS					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	10,193	-	-	-	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	<u>8,300</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct costs	18,493	-	-	-	-
Indirect Costs	<u>7,786</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u><u>26,279</u></u>	<u><u>-</u></u>	<u><u>-</u></u>	<u><u>-</u></u>	<u><u>-</u></u>

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	5-year Budget	Year 1 Budget	YEAR 1 Thru 3/31/02	Funds Remaining (Shortfall)	Proposed Year 2 Budget
3 Arctic Science Education					
3.1 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION ACTIVITIES					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	13,776	8,370	8,376	(6)	2,780
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	16,070	2,316	739	1,577	3,154
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	19,110	-	-	-	3,732
Other Direct Costs	26,488	702	1,851	(1,149)	5,297
Total direct costs	75,444	11,388	10,966	422	14,963
Indirect Costs	31,762	4,794	4,625	169	6,299
Total direct and indirect costs	107,205	16,182	15,591	591	21,262
3.2 ARCTIC VISITING SPEAKERS PROGRAM					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	27,181	7,265	9,601	(2,336)	8,741
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	148,500	29,700	26,370	3,330	29,700
Other Direct Costs	-	-	230	(230)	-
Total direct costs	175,681	36,965	36,201	764	38,441
Indirect Costs	73,962	15,562	15,270	293	16,184
Total direct and indirect costs	249,643	52,527	51,471	1,056	54,625
3.3 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION REPORT					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	9,878	8,368	1,510	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	17,700	17,700	-	-
Total direct costs	-	27,578	26,068	1,510	-
Indirect Costs	-	11,610	10,996	615	-
Total direct and indirect costs	-	39,188	37,064	2,125	-
4 Information and Outreach					
4.1 WITNESS THE ARCTIC NEWSLETTERS					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	93,344	23,699	22,602	1,097	24,759
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	794	(794)	1,577
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	8,035	1,594	-	1,594	-
Other Direct Costs	201,500	35,288	29,859	5,429	51,578
Total direct costs	302,879	60,581	53,255	7,326	77,914
Indirect Costs	127,512	25,505	22,463	3,041	32,802
Total direct and indirect costs	430,391	86,086	75,719	10,367	110,716

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	<u>5-year Budget</u>	<u>Year 1 Budget</u>	<u>YEAR 1 Thru 3/31/02</u>	<u>Funds Remaining (Shortfall)</u>	<u>Proposed Year 2 Budget</u>
4.2 INTERNET RESOURCES					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	372,565	55,527	55,081	446	60,024
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	1,402	1,740	(338)	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	9,947	11,720	(1,773)	7,000
Total direct costs	<u>372,565</u>	<u>66,876</u>	<u>68,542</u>	<u>(1,666)</u>	<u>67,024</u>
Indirect Costs	<u>156,850</u>	<u>28,155</u>	<u>28,911</u>	<u>(756)</u>	<u>28,217</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>529,414</u>	<u>95,031</u>	<u>97,453</u>	<u>(2,422)</u>	<u>95,241</u>

4.3 ARCTIC INFO LISTSERVER					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	98,790	13,797	12,429	1,368	15,086
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	2,478	78	2,400	1,600
Total direct costs	<u>98,790</u>	<u>16,275</u>	<u>12,507</u>	<u>3,768</u>	<u>16,686</u>
Indirect Costs	<u>41,591</u>	<u>6,852</u>	<u>5,276</u>	<u>1,576</u>	<u>7,025</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>140,381</u>	<u>23,127</u>	<u>17,783</u>	<u>5,344</u>	<u>23,711</u>

4.4 DIRECTORY OF ARCTIC RESEARCHERS					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	30,270	7,492	7,933	(441)	7,946
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	8,035	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	1,000	4,140	8,388	(4,248)	4,500
Total direct costs	<u>39,305</u>	<u>11,632</u>	<u>16,321</u>	<u>(4,689)</u>	<u>12,446</u>
Indirect Costs	<u>16,548</u>	<u>4,897</u>	<u>6,884</u>	<u>(1,987)</u>	<u>5,240</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>55,853</u>	<u>16,529</u>	<u>23,205</u>	<u>(6,676)</u>	<u>17,686</u>

4.5 INTERNET GRAPHICS ARCHIVE					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	33,750	-	-	-	7,750
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	30,000	-	-	-	7,500
Total direct costs	<u>63,750</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>15,250</u>
Indirect Costs	<u>26,839</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>6,420</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u>90,588</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>21,671</u>

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	5-year <u>Budget</u>	Year 1 <u>Budget</u>	YEAR 1 Thru <u>3/31/02</u>	Funds Remaining (Shortfall)	Proposed Year 2 <u>Budget</u>
4.6 ARCTIC COMMUNITY OUTREACH					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	60,110	13,977	14,818	(841)	12,474
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	32,140	65	1,417	(1,352)	6,308
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	41,550	2,356	2,356	0	8,130
Other Direct Costs	<u>75,090</u>	<u>29,533</u>	<u>29,121</u>	<u>412</u>	<u>24,515</u>
Total direct costs	208,890	45,931	47,711	(1,780)	51,427
Indirect Costs	<u>87,943</u>	<u>19,337</u>	<u>20,125</u>	<u>(788)</u>	<u>21,651</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u><u>296,833</u></u>	<u><u>65,268</u></u>	<u><u>67,836</u></u>	<u><u>(2,568)</u></u>	<u><u>73,078</u></u>

4.7 PUBLICATION: THE ARCTIC					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	7,143	592	6,551	7,763
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	<u>-</u>	<u>50,970</u>	<u>275</u>	<u>50,695</u>	<u>35,752</u>
Total direct costs	-	58,113	867	57,246	43,515
Indirect Costs	<u>-</u>	<u>9,422</u>	<u>366</u>	<u>9,056</u>	<u>11,267</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u><u>-</u></u>	<u><u>67,534</u></u>	<u><u>1,233</u></u>	<u><u>66,302</u></u>	<u><u>54,782</u></u>

4.8 Endangered Species Consultation Bulletin					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	1,782	2,245	(463)	-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct costs	-	1,782	2,245	(463)	-
Indirect Costs	<u>-</u>	<u>750</u>	<u>947</u>	<u>(197)</u>	<u>-</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u><u>-</u></u>	<u><u>2,532</u></u>	<u><u>3,192</u></u>	<u><u>(660)</u></u>	<u><u>-</u></u>

5 Core Support

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	990,334	163,510	163,554	(44)	200,413
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	86,808	7,734	11,770	(4,036)	17,347
Travel (foreign)	12,054	-	-	-	2,366
Participant Support Costs	-	166	-	166	-
Other Direct Costs	<u>337,800</u>	<u>62,152</u>	<u>91,944</u>	<u>(29,792)</u>	<u>95,845</u>
Total direct costs	1,426,996	233,562	267,267	(33,705)	315,971
Indirect Costs	<u>600,765</u>	<u>98,330</u>	<u>112,733</u>	<u>(14,404)</u>	<u>133,024</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u><u>2,027,761</u></u>	<u><u>331,892</u></u>	<u><u>380,000</u></u>	<u><u>(48,108)</u></u>	<u><u>448,995</u></u>

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TOTAL PROGRAMS					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	2,491,867	533,534	509,010	24,523	540,803
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	317,159	59,463	61,844	(2,381)	65,446
Travel (foreign)	12,054	3,549	-	3,549	5,914
Participant Support Costs	724,447	243,477	149,721	93,756	129,861
Other Direct Costs	999,542	447,131	394,651	52,480	445,838
Total direct costs	<u>4,545,069</u>	<u>1,287,154</u>	<u>1,115,227</u>	<u>171,927</u>	<u>1,187,862</u>
Indirect Costs	<u>1,913,474</u>	<u>526,848</u>	<u>470,403</u>	<u>56,445</u>	<u>493,037</u>
Total direct and indirect costs	<u><u>6,458,543</u></u>	<u><u>1,814,002</u></u>	<u><u>1,585,629</u></u>	<u><u>228,372</u></u>	<u><u>1,680,900</u></u>